

TRANSLATION PRACTICE AT THE MODERN STAGE

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Annotation: The significance of translation at the modern stage is analyzed. The translation functions are considered. Questions are raised about the need for translation practice in the 21st century. Problems multilingualism and related processes.

Key words: Intercultural communication, cultural value of translation, translation practice, translation and dialogue of cultures, multilingualism.

Linguists and psycholinguists have long concluded that learning a foreign language has a positive effect on the intellectual development of the individual, makes comparisons, analyze and synthesize, and most importantly, get acquainted with the culture of another people, thereby expanding their horizons and forming a tolerant attitude towards other cultures.

Recently, interest in multilingualism has especially increased, which has become the norm of communication in many countries. Countries, an inseparable part of the life of peoples. Issues of multilingualism, prospects for its development, as well as related problems of language policy are widely discussed at scientific and practical conferences "round tables" are held on the following topics: "Interaction of cultures and multilingualism", "Aspects of studying and teaching foreign languages", "Translation and features of translation activity", "Analysis and modern interpretation of texts world fiction", etc.

Multilingualism is now considered as a component of economic culture, possession foreign languages as a career engine that most business people need to communicate, correspondence, reading professional literature. Many scientists believe that multilingualism will be able to provide a wide range of interaction and mutual appropriation of the achievements of humanity, the use more powerful

cultural heritage of all civilizations. More and more multilingualism considered as a necessary condition for cooperation in all spheres of life. Knowledge of several foreign languages is nothing more than formula for the successful economic development of any country, many political scientists, economists and other scientists. The experience of Japan is convincing in this respect, the experience of countries that are especially developing such industry as tourism, which is one of the main sources of prosperity for their economy. Consequently, in the context of expanding contacts, both on the interstate and on personal level, knowledge of several languages is required.

In this case, the question arises whether translations from foreign languages are needed, whether translation activity, if the developing multilingualism allows reading works fiction, poetry, texts from different fields of science and technology, without resorting to translation original? Why is it that still scientists in the field of translation theory, linguistics, sociolinguistics, philosophy, psychology and many other areas of science deal with the problems of translation, its techniques and methods. Why is the question still being disputed, what is the main thing in translation - understanding the original and Is it the ultimate translation or is it an interpretation of the original? Is the translation primary or secondary activities? Moreover, many other questions related to translation activity and its difficulties.

However, today there are approximately 7,000 languages on the planet, and the recognized ones are only seven of them are the so-called "world languages", namely English, Spanish, Arabic, Russian, French, German, Portuguese. However, it should be noted that neither in the production of world culture all languages of the world are involved, and without translation, dialogue nor interpretation is possible, which is presented in a global sense as a means of "paving bridges and establishing crossings"

Translation, like language, remains today the universal means of communication between people. He is necessary both in the construction of practical production activities, and in interpersonal contacts, and in communication between peoples, and in the dialogue of cultures. It is customary to define culture as a way of activity, while the functions of culture are nothing more than roles for preserving, ensuring the

whole set of methods and procedures of human activity. Translation functions stem from functions of culture, relating to each other as a part and a whole. Starting its course of history from those times, when contacts arose between different tribes on Earth, translation still has not lost its cultural functions, one of which is the cognitive and educational function. Translation makes the social and spiritual experience of everything accumulated and stored in books the property of all people.

Today there is an opportunity through the Internet to meet and discover many unknown works of scientists from other eras, as well as due to the fact that many aspects of life are receiving new perception and what was previously forbidden becomes available. Appear translations of the works of philosophers that have not been known to this day, and in particular the works of I. G. Fichte, thanks to which scientists can become better acquainted with the views of German philosophers 18-19 centuries and apply for their new research in this area.

The foregoing suggests that translation can have a temporal dimension, linking us not only with modern culture, but also with the culture of bygone times. Through translation, we get the opportunity to "carry on" a dialogue with authors who are chronologically far from us, as he overcomes these temporary barriers. This traces the function of continuity of translation, which contributes to familiarization with the culture of other peoples, while enriching and developing their own culture.

Translation plays an important role in intercultural communication. Translation is special means of communication, a special kind of communicative behavior. Participating in the roll call of cultures, translation allows you to demonstrate a wide range and richness of the culture of speech, introduces readers to incorruptible values of world culture. This function of translation, its cultural value, is precisely lies in the fact that translation not only facilitates the process of interaction of people with each other, it is included in exchange of cultural values - objects, ideas, artistic images and other elements culture. Moreover, it delivers direct satisfaction to a person, serves as a source of acquisition and accumulation of knowledge acquired by humanity throughout its development. Participation translation in the exchange of cultural values makes a significant contribution to world progress. In the modern era, world

cultural contacts take the form of a conscious exchange of cultural values and international cooperation, spiritually enriching each other. Therefore, translation is not just a mediator, but also a creative mediator in this process.

There is a figurative definition of translation work as a labor that cannot be dispensed with, because cultural contents themselves cannot travel, cross borders, for their "transportation" needs an intermediary - a translator.

The activity of a translator in this respect is a special linguistic activity aimed at recreating the original in another language, an activity that requires special training, possession skills and abilities, perfect command of a foreign and native language, knowledge of not only one's own culture, but also the culture of the people, the native speaker of the target language. The translation is determined not only translation from language to language, and from culture to culture.

Translation, being one of the oldest types of human rational activity, is undergoing a stormy development, however, only in the XX century. Various theoretical studies, comparative and contrastive studies at the linguistic level, serve to form the conceptual apparatus translation theory. But if in classical Latin the translation was only a kind of reception Greek culture, pursuing the goal of "reflecting" in someone else's text only the brilliance of their own language, then now a number of requirements are imposed on the translation activity of a person for maximum achievement and understanding of the translated text while maintaining the "face" of the author of the source language.

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